

Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Space Sector

A 2030 Outlook

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1. Drivers of Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Space Sector

The Copernicus programme has created a new ecosystem in Europe around the massive amounts of data produced by its satellites and received daily by its ground segments. In the European security landscape, Space ground segments increasingly appear as potential “new targets” of “new threats”, especially the hybrid ones (e.g. cyber-physical). Indeed, a physical/cyber-attack toward Space ground segment installations or communication networks would cause debilitating impact on public safety and security of European citizens and could affect also other European critical infrastructures through cascading effects. On the one hand, a physical attack on a space ground segment could make the distribution of satellite data problematic and, on the other hand, a cyber-attack in its data storage, access and exchange could affect not only the confidentiality and integrity of space data, but also their FAIR standards: findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability [1]. Global satellite ground station market revenue is expected to increase by USD 181.4 Billion by 2032, with a 12.8% CAGR from 2023 to 2032 [2].

Figure 1: Satellite Ground Station (SGS) Market Analysis (Source: Acumen Research and Consulting)

Back in 2020, the **H2020 7SHIELD project** [3], dealt with the topic that space is the new frontier in cyber security. Due to the growing reliance on satellite communications for today's economy and governments, the ground segments of space systems receive massive amounts of satellite data. Any physical or cyber-attack against the storage, access or exchange of this data would pose a major public safety threat. The EU-funded 7SHIELD project developed a holistic framework enabling the deployment of innovative services for the cyber-physical protection of ground segments. The project deployed TRL-7 solutions (most involving humans-in-the-loop) to assess physical and cyber risks and prepare Ground Segments' protection, in order to enhance preparedness, detect, respond, mitigate, and effectively prepare to cyber and physical threats. The expected result was an integrated yet flexible and adaptable framework enabling the deployment of innovative services for cyber-physical protection of ground segments, such as e-fences, passive radars and laser technologies, multimedia AI technologies. The project made use of advanced technologies for data integration, processing, analytics and visualisation as well as data security and cyberthreat protection to assess the prevention, detection and mitigation of threats, both physical and cyber.

It is fundamental to have an overview about the Space Ground Segment (GS) before illustrating current trends and market drivers.

1.1. The Space Ground Segment

The Space Ground Segment (GS) consists of an ensemble of facilities responsible for the acquisition, processing, distribution and archiving of the satellite data and of their derived products [4]. These facilities and their operators vary with the nature of the data collected by the satellites. There are three main types of Space Ground Segments: Earth Observation (EO) GS, Satellite Communication (SATCOM) GS and Navigation (GNSS) GS.

- **Earth Observation** refers to the use of remote sensing technologies to monitor land, marine (rivers, lakes) and atmosphere. Satellite-based EO relies on the use of satellite mounted payloads to gather imaging data about the Earth's characteristics. The images are then processed and analysed in order to extract different types of information that can serve a very wide range of applications and industries [5].
- **Satellite communication** refers to the use of satellites to relay and amplify radio telecommunications signals via a transponder. It creates a communication channel between a source transmitter and a receiver at different locations on Earth. Communications satellites are used for television, telephone, radio, internet, and military applications.
- **Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)** refers to a constellation of satellites providing signals from space that transmit positioning and timing data to GNSS receivers. The receivers then use this data to determine location.

1.2. Ground Segment trends and market drivers

The market for satellite ground stations has witnessed significant growth in recent years. This growth can be attributed to the increasing demand for satellite-based communication services, such as broadband internet, broadcasting, navigation, remote sensing, and military applications. With the proliferation of small satellites and mega-constellations, there is a greater need for a robust and reliable ground station infrastructure to manage and control these satellites effectively. Moreover, advancements in satellite technology, including high-throughput satellites and software-defined ground stations, have driven the adoption of more sophisticated ground station solutions.

- **A Sustained growth in Earth Observation data volumes**

The volume of Earth Observation data produced by large-scale open data programmes (Copernicus, Landsat, Gaofen etc.) and stored on EO platforms is booming for a decade and is expected to continue growing for years to come. This growth has accelerated with the arrival of many private NewSpace players such as Planet, IceEye, Capella Space, Satellogic, SpaceWill or Zhuhai Orbita Aerospace, all targeting large-scale small EO satellites constellation. In 2022, the 68 millionth data package was published on the Open Hub and on average almost 40,000 data packages were published per day. Moreover, the number of registered users on the Open Hub increased again, from 496,382 users at the end of Y2021 to 638,259 by the end of 2022, and there were 108 countries across the world with more than 500 registered users, a rise from 96 at the end of Y2021. These figures suggest that more and more users around the world are starting to engage with the potential contained in the vast stores of free and open data available through the Copernicus Data Access System [6].

The sustained growth in the volume of Earth Observation data generates a sustained demand for EO ground segment facilities such as ground stations, data storage, processing and distribution capacities.

- **An increasing demand for satellite-based communication services**

The increasing demand for satellite-based communication services like inflight connectivity, maritime broadband services along with growth of telecommunication sector is anticipated to generate demand for new communication satellite launches.

Figure 2: Global satellite capacity supply & demand (Source: NRS 2020 17th edition)

Commercial satellite operators are investing heavily into construction and deployment of Geosynchronous Equatorial Orbit (GEO) high throughput satellites. The satellite and space industries are in the most exciting phase of their history, where innovation, large-scale investments, and the realization of ROI will lead to further growth and risk-taking. Although satellite communications remain a niche in the overall telecommunications market, its overall importance, impact, and network role will increase over time. NSR's Satellite Capacity Supply & Demand, 20th Edition (SCSD20) [7] observes the rapid rise in LEO satellites have forever altered the satellite capacity market, shifting it from high priced wholesale centric to one driven by near commodity pricing, value-added offerings and telco integration. Massive LEO/MEO supply, coupled with innovative ground segment technology now makes satellite offerings more relevant than ever to the broader telecom industry.

With over \$257 billion in satellite capacity revenue projected over the next decade, it is clear LEO satellites are a critical enabler of this growth. The increasing demand for high throughput satellites to address new services (IFE, M2M /IoT etc.) and new geographical areas is sustaining the demand for SATCOM ground segment facilities such as ground stations [8].

- **An increasing number of ground segment infrastructures**

According to Euroconsult [9], space ground segment ecosystem undergoing profound transformation and expansion in response to evolving satcom and Earth observation demands. In the EO ground segment, the number of ground stations is steadily growing to serve the increasing demand on EO data and value-added services. At ground station level, specific trends are emerging in different segments. Across the commercial sector, robust investments in High-Throughput Satellite (HTS) and Very High-Throughput Satellite (VHTS) systems, particularly in NGSO constellations, are driving growth in the data and services market. The dynamic evolution of the space segment, with flexible payloads and constellations, underscores the need for adaptable ground infrastructure to support advanced communication needs. Evolutions in the way satellite operators gather and transmit information to the ground is driving growth for ground segment operators. In particular, adoption of high-throughput satellite (HTS) technology means more, stronger antennas will be needed to receive higher volumes of data transmission. Satellites are also shifting up in the frequency bands they're using to transmit data and messages back to Earth. Ka-band utilization is booming, and additional ground segments will be necessary to meet the demand as well to prepare for the anticipated increase in the utilization of other bands, including V-band frequencies [10]. With the exponential growth of satellites in space showing no signs of slowing down, Euroconsult is considering the growing need for supportive ground infrastructure to back up assets in orbit. The ground segment market will reach a cumulative value of \$80bn by 2032, according to the report titled Ground Segment Market Prospects from Euroconsult [11].

- **An increasing need for secure spectrum usage**

As a result of the increasing need for secure spectrum usage, National Authorities charged with spectrum monitoring heavily invest in more sophisticated and efficient Spectrum monitoring tools. The investment is driven by the need to secure spectrum for reliable communications in an environment where more and more spectrum is used by operators, the co-sharing of spectrum is increasing with more and more complex techniques, the protection of the provided service to the end user is of high priority as well as the fast response, the detection and the termination of an interference coming from earth stations (fixed or mobile) or satellites. High traffic and Internet of Things (IoT) are expected to grow and deploy everywhere and need for monitoring is increasing.

- **The development of a new business model: The Ground Segment as a Service**

A new demand for Ground-Segment-as-a-Service (GSaaS) is emerging, especially driven by EO constellation operators. These constellations typically need a global network of ground infrastructure with relatively low contact time per satellite. GSaaS offers ground station services to legacy and NewSpace operators unwilling or lacking the resources to develop a dedicated ground segment. This model is similar to a “shared economy” approach, with by-the-minute or per-pass pricing. Additionally, subscription or flat rate models comparable to the traditional dedicated antenna model exist. Providers offering satellite-to-ground communication services, such as GSaaS, are enabling satellite operators to shift ground segment costs from capital expenditure (CAPEX) to operational expenditure (OPEX), mainly driven by Earth observation (EO) requirements. It's particularly relevant for new operators testing their business models and aiming for progressive scaling. The Ground Station as a Service (GSaaS) market grew at an 11% CAGR during the last five years and is expected to

continue expanding to reach \$400 million by 2027 [12]. GSaaS is experiencing strong market pull from NewSpace operators looking to convert CAPEX into OPEX, especially for LEO applications. By outsourcing the ground segment operating expenditure, satellite operators can lower the upfront investment as well as the inherent risk of commercial failure. Changing requirements can quickly and easily be accommodated, and even complete pivots in technical requirements or business model aren't hindered by ownership of ground assets. In turn, ground segment providers with expertise and enough customer aggregation can offer a multitude of capabilities and accommodate changing requirements, all while benefiting from the increase in demand for services. Big Tech companies not traditionally active in the space industry (such as Amazon Web Services and Microsoft) have also entered the ground segment market. This is in part due to the parallels of including an as-a-Service component in their portfolios, and the leveraging of their big Data Centres assets and Data Analytics capabilities. Together with technological developments such as AI for ground segment operations, ground segment virtualisation and flat panel antennas, these new forces may provide a further boost to GSaaS as well as the entirety of the ground segment market. Players in the ground segment and GSaaS market include legacy technology companies, ground station and satellite operators with decades of experience (e.g., GMV, Indra, KSAT, SSC). Agile NewSpace entrants such as Atlas Space Operations, LeafSpace, Infostellar, and Contec, as well as Big Tech companies looking to diversify their cloud offering (e.g., AWS, Microsoft Azure) also play an important role. There might also be opportunities for infrastructure-as-a-service players with technical expertise or facilities in favourable geographic locations. While inevitably some will fail over time, current developments suggest that small NewSpace players as well as legacy operators and big tech all have a place in the market [13]. These new entrants to the Space Ground Segment ecosystem contribute to the development of ground infrastructure and its economic growth.

Figure 3: Ground segment is increasingly experiencing disruption from players adopting New Space practices and those offering additional space sector or other technical capabilities.

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- **The Physical technologies are mature**

Physical and logical security technologies have matured to the point that they can now be integrated. The convergence of the IP network and the migration of legacy sensors and appliances to TCP/IP are helping drive this transformation. Cameras are now IP-based; card readers use the IP network instead of a proprietary network; and access lists, policies, and procedures are stored and generated by computers [1].

- **The security budgets of companies are increasing**

The complex landscape and the growing threats are leading companies and institutions to increase their security budgets, particularly for critical infrastructure protection. The major factors driving the market include the increasing cyber-attacks on the systems deployed.

According to Markets and Markets, the global critical infrastructure protection market size as per revenue was worth approximately USD 143.0 billion in 2023 and is poised to generate revenue around USD 162.5 billion by the end of 2027, projecting a CAGR of 3.3%.

Three primary drivers are pushing better security in critical infrastructures:

- Increasing cyber-attacks on the system deployed
- Lack of interoperability between CIP solutions
- Rise in the usage and adoption of the Internet of Things [14]

The current whitepaper examines the primary obstacles that space and GS enterprises must overcome in order to safeguard their vital assets in current security environment. Moreover, it offers suggestions for space and GS institutions as well as other stakeholders, along with solutions that can successfully address these issues.

2. Challenges and Limitations

Some of the main challenges and limitation faced by satellite operators in the scope of their cyber-security and critical infrastructure protection efforts include:

- **Challenge 1 – Regulation**

The capacity for satellite operators to invest in dedicated ground stations will be heavily influenced by the evolution of national regulatory schemes. The latter today can make it hard for satellite operators to predict the date of completion and activation of their ground stations. Furthermore, these delays vary from one country to another, as the licensing frameworks (i.e. procedures, fees, etc.) are not harmonized on a global scale. Such harmonization could make it easier and faster for satellite operators to obtain licenses worldwide, and thus could facilitate the ground station building. Industry experts consider that the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) already attempts to streamline and provide various paths for licensing, which is expected to alleviate various pain points experienced by satellite operators. However, if the regulatory framework does not evolve to adapt to the increasing satellite activity (i.e. forecasts show increasing satellites operated in the future), ground segment licensing could become an even bigger hurdle for satellite operators that wish to establish their own ground stations. Finally, geopolitical conflicts could also prevent some countries to install ground stations in non-allied countries. In such situations, the development of Ground Stations could be more limited than expected [1][3].

• **Challenge 2 - Funding**

As the satellite industry becomes competitive, ground station operators may find it difficult to obtain finance for the expensive investments required to build and maintain satellite ground stations. To fund their operations and expansion ambitions, operators may need to look for funding from a variety of sources. The high expenses of constructing and operating satellite ground stations, the need for lengthy expenditures, and the dangers of the satellite sector are just a few of the factors that may make it difficult for commercial ground station operators to obtain funding. It costs a lot of money to build and maintain satellite ground stations. Financing is difficult since satellite ground station investments are long-term in nature. In order to create the required infrastructure, ground station operators must invest a large sum of money up front, and the profits on that investment might not be seen for several years. Moreover, spending on satellite ground station infrastructure frequently necessitates expensive, long-term upkeep and improvements. Last but not least, the risks involved with the satellite sector could make funding more difficult. The satellite sector faces a number of hazards, such as governmental obstacles, technological obsolescence, and competition from new players. When looking for financing, ground station operators must take these risks into account because they could affect the investment's feasibility [1][3].

• **Challenge 3 - Satellite Communication Infrastructure**

In this digital era, reliable and uninterrupted connectivity is a necessity for individuals and businesses across the globe. While traditional terrestrial networks have played a significant role in meeting this demand, they often fall short in areas with challenging geographical terrains, remote locations, or during natural disasters. Although satellite communication offers immense potential, there are challenges associated with building a resilient network infrastructure that must be addressed. Satellite communication infrastructure plays a vital role in bridging connectivity gaps in areas with challenging geographical terrains or during emergencies. Latency, bandwidth constraints, costs, weather interference, and space debris are common challenges associated with satellite communication:

- Latency: Satellite communication typically introduces a higher latency compared to traditional terrestrial networks. The distance signals must travel between Earth and satellites causes increased round-trip times. However, with advancements in technology, this latency challenge is gradually being minimized.
- Bandwidth Constraints: Satellite networks traditionally had limited bandwidth capabilities, resulting in lower data transfer rates. However, with the emergence of High-Throughput Satellites (HTS), these limitations are being overcome, enabling higher data rates and improved capacity.
- Costs: Building and maintaining satellite communication infrastructure involves significant costs, making it less feasible for smaller organizations or remote communities. However, advancements in technology and increased competition in the industry have led to cost reductions, making satellite communication more accessible.
- Weather Interference: Adverse weather conditions such as rain fade, thunderstorms, or heavy cloud coverage can affect signal quality and result in temporary disruptions. Implementing technologies and strategies to mitigate weather interference is crucial for maintaining uninterrupted connectivity.
- Space Debris: The growing number of satellites in space and the associated space debris pose a risk to existing and future satellite networks. Organizations are now focusing on space environment management and implementing strategies to safeguard communication infrastructure from potential collisions.

Advancements in satellite technology, hybrid network architectures, dynamic bandwidth allocation, weather monitoring, and space debris tracking are strategies utilized to overcome these challenges. Improving satellite technology, such as the introduction of High-Throughput Satellites, enhances network performance and capacity. Hybrid network architectures intelligently combine satellite and terrestrial networks to provide seamless connectivity in remote or challenging areas. Dynamic bandwidth allocation optimizes resource utilization to overcome traditional bandwidth constraints effectively. Weather monitoring systems and adaptive technologies help mitigate weather interference and ensure uninterrupted connectivity. Space debris tracking and mitigation strategies safeguard satellite infrastructure and promote long-term sustainability. Building a resilient network addressing satellite communication infrastructure challenges requires a combination of cutting-edge technology, strategic planning, and proactive measures. As the demand for connectivity continues to grow, the industry must overcome these challenges to provide reliable and uninterrupted access to individuals and businesses worldwide [15].

- **Challenge 4 - Physical and cyber-attacks**

Space components themselves, such as satellites, have also become more vulnerable to physical and cyber-attacks. As satellites cannot locally store and process large amounts of data, they need to link up with a ground station to download their recorded data. However, the building and maintenance of such ground stations is expensive and vulnerable to disruption and cyber-attacks. Having recognised this, major companies like Amazon, Microsoft and Tencent are now offering their satellite systems' ground stations to third parties. These include small companies, states, as well as international organisations. This business model is called 'Ground Station as a Service (GSaaS)'. GSaaS is essentially a response to the demand for 'big data' which has caused a shift to additional services being offered to users, allowing them to use the integrated data generated by satellites [16]. What enables the exchange of data between the end user, the ground station, and the relevant satellites is the cyber domain. Hence, a successful attack on any of these parts could compromise both an actor's cyber and space capabilities. With ground stations being the weakest link, these are particularly vulnerable to attacks, and consequently require a high degree of security and resilience.

- **Challenge 5 - The Cyber-attacks are increasing in number and in sophistication**

For a decade, cyber-attacks are increasing in number and in sophistication all around the world. The costs induced by these attacks have jumped by +12% in 2019 and by +72% in 5 years according to Accenture's ninth annual cost of cybercrime study [17]. At the same time, risks of physical attacks by terrorists or activists remain high and very hard to predict. Global cybercrime costs rose from \$3 trillion in 2015 and are expected to reach \$10.5 trillion USD annually by 2025—the size of the world's third-biggest economy after the United States and China, according to research published by Cybersecurity Ventures [18]. The number of cyberattacks has been on the rise in recent years, with cybercriminals using a variety of tactics to gain unauthorized access to computer systems and steal, expose, alter, disable, or destroy data, applications or other assets. Cyberattacks can be launched for all sorts of reasons, from petty theft to acts of war. The average cost of a data breach is USD 4.35 million, which includes the costs of discovering and responding to the violation, downtime and lost revenue, and the long-term reputational damage to a business and its brand. Ransomware attacks have commanded ransom payments as high as USD 40 million. Cyberattacks that compromise customers' personally identifiable information (PII) can lead to a loss of customer trust, regulatory fines, and even legal action. By one estimate, cybercrime will cost the world economy USD 10.5 trillion per year by 2025 [19].

- **Challenge 6 - The interfaces between Physical and Digital assets are increasing**

Cybersecurity depends greatly on physical security. Attackers who can gain physical access to a computer can almost always take advantage of that access to further their efforts. Merely getting access to a physical terminal where a memory device can be plugged in is usually sufficient. Any device present that is connected to the network must be physically protected to ensure that it cannot be turned into a tool to be used in an attack [1].

- **Challenge 7 - The security supervision systems market is fragmented**

The market of security supervision systems is divided in three main segments:

- The **Physical Security Information Management (PSIM)** systems that centralise data streams from physical sensors and equipment (CCTV, face recognition, plate recognition, badges, guards, barriers etc.) and monitor equipment, people behaviour and building access. According to Mordor Intelligence (<https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/physical-security-information-management-market>), the global physical security information management market is estimated at USD 1.66 billion in 2024, and is expected to reach USD 3.53 billion by 2029, growing at a CAGR of 16.24% during the forecast period (2024-2029) [20]. One of the major drivers of the market's growth includes increasing government and defense initiatives to implementing PSIM solutions to improve their current security systems beyond simple video surveillance. The physical security information management market is fragmented, owing to the presence of multiple players in the market. The solution provider is dependent on other value chain enablers, such as cloud service providers, which impacts their revenue aspects. Vendors with multiple functions and business units are better placed in the market, as they have an extended reach in the supply chain, which assists them in providing their services. Some key players in the market include Johnson Controls International PLC, CNL Software Ltd, Genetec Inc, Qognify Inc., Verint Systems Inc. and Vidsys Inc.
- The **Security Information and Event Management (SIEM)** systems that centralise data streams from digital sensors and equipment (firewall, anti-malware, logbook etc.) and monitor applications, user behaviour and data access. According to MarketandMarket [21], Information and Event Management (SIEM) market size is expected to grow from USD 4.2 billion in 2020 to USD 5.5 billion by 2025, at a CAGR of 5.5% during the forecast period. The major vendors covered in the Security Information and Event Management Market include SolarWinds (US), IBM (US), Micro Focus (UK), Rapid7 (US), RSA (US), McAfee (US), Splunk (US), ManageEngine (US), LogRhythm (US), Sumo Logic (US), Exabeam (US), Securonix (US), Alert Logic (US), Graylog (US), BlackStratus (US), AlienVault (US), Fortinet (US), LogPoint (Denmark), Gurukul (US), and Cygiant (US).
- The **Network Management Systems (NMS)** that monitors, maintains and optimises network activities. They are generally used to monitor IT networks but some systems can monitor networks or physical equipment. According to MarketsAndMarkets [22], the global Network Management System Market size as per revenue was surpassed USD 9.3 billion in 2022 and it is anticipated to exhibit a CAGR of 9.4% to rise over USD 14.6 billion by the end of 2027. The rise in demand for NMS across SMEs would offer opportunities for the growth of the market. Furthermore, the increasing need for in-depth visibility into network security, and growing demand for better optimisation of business operations have led to a wider demand for NMS. The increasing need for in-depth visibility into network security and Quality of Service (QoS) and growing network infrastructure are major factors expected to drive the growth of the NMS market. Exponential growth in the global Internet Protocol (IP) traffic and

cloud traffic, and prominence of the Internet of Things (IoT) are expected to offer vast market opportunities for NMS vendors in the next five years.

The above list of challenges is not exhaustive, yet representative of some key security risks that must be addressed by modern critical infrastructure operators.

3. Solution Guidelines: Towards new CIP Capabilities and Resilience

Comprehensive solution guidelines are provided to strengthen the space industry's Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) capabilities and resilience. Due to the increasing interdependencies between physical and digital assets and also to the evolution of cyberattacks that are becoming more sophisticated, cyber and physical security measures are convergent. The implementation of a holistic security framework including innovative technology, such as artificial intelligence, predictive data analytics, threat detection and mitigation tools, is emphasised as a priority in the guidelines. The management of the increasing risks to satellite data assets, ground segments, and space systems depends on these technologies. The guidelines are divided into four categories: technical and technological guidelines collaboration, regulatory support, and training. They underline the necessity for effective cybersecurity measures, space traffic management systems, satellite shielding, automated terrestrial infrastructure, and quantum communication technologies. The text also emphasizes the significance of adhering to international norms and laws, updating CIP policies and procedures on a regular basis, and implementing a worldwide strategy for CIP in space. Furthermore, it underlines the necessity of continuing training, risk management education, and collaborative learning to keep pace with the growing space business. Regarding cooperation, the rules promote the establishment of networks and alliances between diverse stakeholders, such as governmental organizations, educational establishments, and law enforcement agencies. The goal of this cooperative method is to stimulate innovation and improve the security management procedure. The space industry hopes to improve its CIP skills by adhering to these recommendations, which will safeguard critical infrastructures' security and resilience in the face of ever-changing threats and technological breakthroughs. Specifically, the following solution guidelines are envisaged:

3.1. Technical and Technological Guidelines

The sustained growth in the volume of data passing through satellite ground segments, the criticality of these data for a number of services and industries, the growing number of cyber-attacks around the world, the increasing costs they induce for the targeted companies and institutions, the increasing complexity of the attacks, the increasing interfaces between physical and digital assets, the maturity of the TCP/IP technologies etc. All that calls for the convergence of cybersecurity and physical security. This convergence is a topic discussed for years by security leaders, but the solutions proposed are still at their infancy. There is thus a real need for the development of a holistic framework for Ground Segment protection against Cyber and Physical threats, that integrate advanced technologies. To address the above-listed challenges there is need for developing, adopting and deploying novel CIP solutions for the critical infrastructures of the space sector. The proposed solutions should cover: forecast, assessment of physical and cyber risks, prevention, detection, response, and in case of failure, mitigation of consequences (including novel installation designs), and fast recovery after incidents, over the life span of the infrastructure, with a view to achieving the security and resilience of all functions performed by the installations, and of neighbouring populations and the environment. A holistic platform which integrates novelty technological achievements covering the risk analysis

phases: Prevention technologies for C/P Threats, Detection technologies for C/P Threats, Response technologies for C/P Threats and Mitigation technologies for C/P Threats. Encapsulate robust, accurate and automated state-of-the-art technologies originated by multidisciplinary fields, such as C/P Threat Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence and Predictive Data Analytics, Decision Support Systems for Crisis Management and Risk Assessment, Image and Video processing to face and object detection, UAVs processing, laser-based detection techniques, resilience-oriented interactive visualisations that will enable to deploy reliable situational awareness and more efficient decision-making processes across all the phases of risk management.

- **Prevention technologies for physical and cyber threats:** These technologies will assess the vulnerability of each asset of the space ground segment, whether it is some mechanic component or data asset. The foreseen technologies which contribute to the pre-crisis phase involve also analytical prediction models for future threats, secure authentication mechanism for data access and cascade effects from combined cyber-physical attacks.
- **Detection technologies for physical and cyber threats:** Detection technologies to seamlessly and accurately identify potential physical or/and cyber threats to Space Systems, ground Segments and Satellite data assets.
- **Response technologies for physical and cyber threats:** Innovative technologies to monitor the evolvement of a physical or/and cyber-attacks, to strengthen the responsiveness and social awareness.
- **Mitigation technologies for physical and cyber threats:** Appropriate actions to mitigate the consequences of physical and cyber-attacks, focusing on the services continuity.

The space sector's role in CIP is evolving rapidly, driven by a host of innovative technologies and solutions. These advancements are not only addressing current challenges but also reshaping the way we approach the protection of space-based critical infrastructure [1][3].

• **Guideline 1 - Implementation of a holistic security framework**

The adoption of a holistic framework covering both cyber and physical threats protection, seems to be a highly trendy topic for CIP for some time now. Despite the strong demand for such holistic system of systems, several critical factors seem to emerge and need to be considered as critical guidelines in the adoption of such a framework:

- The modularity: Potential customers want to limit both investment costs and technological risks. It is thus mandatory for this framework to be modular and easily interfaced with existing devices, software and infrastructures. So that any customer can choose just what he needs to complete its holistic security framework while being sure that it will work smoothly.
- The ergonomics: Implementing a new system is always a risk as it implies a period of adaptation for the operating team and necessitates a wide adoption by all the stakeholders to generate its full benefits. These aspects are even more crucial when dealing with security matters and critical infrastructures, since no security weakness is allowed. The ergonomics of such a framework is thus a key success criterion to shorten the period of adaptation, increase and fasten its adoption at large scale and thus lower induced risks for critical infrastructure operators.
- The cost efficiency and ROI: As any investment, the people in charge of infrastructure security must justify the Return On Investment to get the budget. The framework should clearly demonstrate the cost efficiency to merge cyber and physical security management.

- The efficiency: Critical infrastructures cannot offer any weakness. It is thus mandatory for Chief Security Officers to be reassured of the efficiency of any solution before implementing on their infrastructure.
- **Guideline 2 - Advanced Cybersecurity Measures:** The adoption of cutting-edge cybersecurity technologies is critical. This includes the development of sophisticated encryption techniques, intrusion detection systems, and AI-driven threat analysis tools. These technologies are essential for safeguarding data integrity and ensuring secure communication between space assets and ground stations.
- **Guideline 3 - Space Traffic Management Systems:** New systems for space traffic management are needed to face the current issues related to satellite congestion and space debris. These systems use innovative technologies such as enhanced radar and optical sensors, machine learning, and sophisticated algorithms to identify and anticipate the movements of space objects, reducing the frequency of accidents.
- **Guideline 4 - Robust Satellite Shielding and Hardening:** New developments in satellite architecture have led to stronger shielding against physical and space weather hazards as well as better resistance against cyber and electronic warfare assaults through hardening approaches.
- **Guideline 5 - Automated and Resilient Ground Segment Infrastructure:** Resilient designs are integrated with automation to strengthen the ground segment infrastructure. In order to guarantee uninterrupted operation and management of space assets, this involves redundant systems, fail-safe processes, and the capacity to quickly recover from disturbances.
- **Guideline 6 - Integrated Data Analysis and Decision Support Systems:** To improve situational awareness and assist in CIP decision-making, integrated data analysis systems are being created by utilizing big data analytics and artificial intelligence. Large volumes of data from several sources may be processed by these systems, giving rise to insightful information for threat detection and response.
- **Guideline 7 - Quantum Communication and Encryption:** Secure space communications can advance significantly with the use of quantum technologies, especially in communication and encryption. Theoretically impenetrable, quantum encryption has the potential to completely transform how sensitive data is handled.

3.2. Regulatory Support Guidelines

In Europe, the European Union is leading policy development actions on cyber and physical threats with the objective to ensure the security and resilience of the EU member states' critical infrastructure and networks. EU cyber security policy has been and still is a steady evolution of policies and initiatives designed to improve the EU's cyber security posture and resilience. The EU sees establishing strong policies not only as a means to protect citizens and assets but also for building a competitive and innovative EU security industry. Europe has a long existing emphasis on creating and maintaining standards for its space industry. The ECSS and CEN/CENELEC Space standards, the standards cover products, components and production standards. Specific security standards are in drafting by ECSS. For Space missions, security requirements are made applicable and provided as

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requirements or as annexes to the contractual conditions with the responsibility being with the contractor to demonstrate the requirements are met. Accreditation processes are used to ensure the resulting ground segment meets the required security requirements.

- **Guideline 8 – Standardization and Regulation Compliance:** Strive toward the globalization of CIP for space practices and technology. Respecting international laws and guidelines can provide a high quality of protection for various countries and businesses. Adopt a standardisation and policy-making approach with the main aim to standardise and demonstrate strategies and policies to prevent, early detect, response and mitigate of amalgamated attacks in physical and cyber manner. It is fundamental to improve the security and resilience of infrastructure in Europe and globally. This activity needs to explore the current and proposed European policy framework regulating electronic communications operations to understand the current policy requirements and make policy recommendations. The main focus needs to be in particular on how the current policies could influence the solutions and what gaps in the policies are present that need to be put in place to make it possible to fully implement innovative technologies. The standards helped in the process of innovation for the development of both strategic and operational guidelines dedicated for the ground segments. In this sense, the standards provided the basis for establishing clear and specific communication channels, specific roles and responsibilities for the ground segment's stakeholders, the definition of specific incident management tasks that need to be performed at each organizational level, as well as provisions for the cooperation between levels within a single ground segment but also between multiple stakeholders outside the ground segment per se (police authorities, ESA etc.). Therefore, the standards formulated the model upon which specific, dedicated and tailor-made emergency response guidelines were created, facilitating timely and effective decision making for the containment of an emergency and leading towards the recovery of a ground segment's operations. Standards supported the innovation from the technical point of view, given that a) allowed effective distribution of emergency information with improved standardization and ability to be tailored for user needs, and b) allowed the understanding of the complex relationships that exist between organizations, systems, and systems-of-systems, also enabling the analysis of these systems to ensure that they meet the expectations of the end users [23].
- **Guideline 9 - Compliance with National Regulations:** Because Space Ground Segments are identified as critical infrastructures there is an obligation to take measures to protect them from cyber and physical threats. The obligations are strongly driven by EU, national and regional regulations. Space agencies, national and European must therefore protect their critical infrastructures and assets which flows down to the designers, developers and operators. Also, in increasing numbers, private Ground Segment owners are operating systems that need continuity of service. They too will need to comply with national regulations.
- **Guideline 10 – Regularly Updated Standards, Policies and Procedures:** Make sure that CIP policies and procedures in the space industry are routinely evaluated and modified to take into account the most recent developments in technology and danger scenarios. Organisations that are active in the Space business domain and significantly involved IT related aspects felt that they were sufficiently aware of the applicable standards for their work. Others (the majority), specifically in the areas where new technologies were being introduced it was felt that review of the standards has made the importance of knowledge of standards

more relevant for their work. Particularly to effectively utilise the technologies, a better understanding of standards is needed.

- **Guideline 11 – Requirements identification:** Identify a set of requirements including the security requirements that are applicable for a wide range of Space Ground Segments fulfilling the needs of the stakeholders, but primarily the Ground Segment developers and operators. Understand the possible impact of ethics and legal frameworks on the implementation of new technologies.
- **Guideline 12 – Collaborative International Frameworks and Standards:** Underline the significance of creating cooperative worldwide norms and procedures for CIP in the space industry. These kinds of projects seek to standardize procedures, promote information exchange, and guarantee a unified worldwide reaction to dangers [23].

3.3. Training, Reskilling and Upskilling Guidelines

For the space industry to respond to risks and fast changing technology, training, reskilling, and upskilling are essential.

- **Guideline 13 – Adopt valuable instruction and training:** A uniform approach to instruction and training guarantees that staff members have the abilities and know-how required to properly oversee and safeguard space-based infrastructure. By focusing on high-quality, validated training practices, the sector can streamline processes, enhance productivity, and minimize risks associated with the implementation and operation of complex space systems. Adhering to best practices in these areas ensures a standardised and efficient approach to system improvement and development. Moreover, high-quality training results in end-products that meet or exceed user expectations. Incorporating best practices into training offers significant advantages for both developing new systems and enhancing existing ones. These best practices, crafted by experts, provide a standardised approach ensuring consistency across various components and systems. The adoption of these best practices in training offers two primary benefits:
 - **Efficiency in Implementation:** Designed to optimise processes by eliminating redundant steps, these best practices significantly enhance productivity. They provide a clear, streamlined path for users to adopt innovative technologies, ensuring a smoother transition and quicker integration into existing systems.
 - **Risk Minimization:** These practices are structured to reduce errors and incorrect usage, thereby enhancing the reliability and stability of the systems developed. By following these guidelines, users can mitigate potential risks associated with system implementation and operation.
- **Guideline 14 – Support Business Continuity Management System with Training:** Every organization needs to develop its own dynamic Business Continuity Management System (BCMS) based on its unique characteristics. In this process, the identification of the major faced risks along with the development of the corresponding response procedures, the training and the testing of such steps are deemed to be crucial parameters that largely affect the effectiveness of a BCMS. In particular, training and testing is an iterative optimization process that involves initially developing a test methodology, in which the simultaneous testing and training of the disaster recovery team is followed by a BC revision to improve its efficiency, and consequently this is followed by a simultaneous testing and training phase.

- **Guideline 15 – Emphasis on Practical Application:** To foster a deeper comprehension of systems and technology, training should be grounded in real-world scenarios and practical application.
- **Guideline 16 – Frequent Updates of Skills:** Training programs must be updated on a frequent basis to ensure that skills remain current and relevant as threats and technology change.
- **Guideline 17 – Stress Continuous Learning:** Since the space industry is always changing, training curricula should be revised often to incorporate the most recent advancements and industry best practices.
- **Guideline 18 – Risk Management Education:** Include thorough risk management techniques in training to get staff members ready for any obstacles that may arise during space operations.
- **Guideline 19 – Collaborative Learning Approaches:** Promote collaborative learning settings to share best practices and stimulate innovation across the space industry community.
- **Guideline 20 – Input-Driven Improvement:** Set up systems for receiving input so that training curricula are regularly improved and made to better suit the changing demands of industry.
- **Guideline 21 – Streamlined Processes:** To increase productivity and efficiency, try to streamline and simplify training procedures by eliminating pointless stages.

These guidelines will help in cultivating a workforce that is not only technically proficient but also adaptable to the unique demands of the space sector [1][3][23].

3.4. Collaboration Guideline

Collaboration in the space sector is crucial, involving a diverse network of actors including governmental authorities, academic institutions, and security agencies. This collaborative approach facilitates a comprehensive exchange of information and ideas, enriching the overall security management process.

- **Guideline 22 – Networks and Partnership:** By building networks and partnerships, the space sector can leverage a wide range of expertise and perspectives, leading to enhanced outcomes in security and operational efficiency. Collaboration with a wide number of actors in the whole security management cycle, governmental authorities and academic institutes, as well as to the security agencies needs to be fundamental. Building networks and collaboration with other stakeholders ensures a proper exchange information and ideas and enriches the results and outcomes. The principal aim of this action is to collate information and experiences, to benefit from other outcomes, methodologies, best practices and success stories, to foster networking to perform profitable and fruitful collaborations.
- **Guideline 23 – Create Multi-Stakeholder Forums:** Provide venues for different stakeholders to communicate, exchange ideas, and work together on projects.
- **Guideline 24 – Promote Academic-Industrial Partnerships:** To integrate theoretical research with real-world application, promote cooperation between academic institutions and industrial participants. Promoting innovation ecosystems and public-private collaborations

are essential for propelling technical developments in CIP. In order to coordinate efforts and hasten the creation of novel solutions, this entails setting up venues for cooperation between governmental organizations, business leaders, and academic institutions.

- **Guideline 25 – Regular Knowledge Exchange Programs:** Arrange conferences and seminars to facilitate ongoing exchange of cutting-edge techniques, fresh findings, and innovations in technology.
- **Guideline 26 – Collaborative Research and Development:** Take part in cooperative R&D projects to address difficult problems and provide novel solutions for the space industry.
- **Guideline 27 – Cross-Sector Cooperation:** Encourage collaboration across many industries, including IT, defense, and telecommunications, that can support space security.
- **Guideline 28 – International Cooperation and Information Sharing:** Take part in global cooperation to exchange threat intelligence and plan coordinated countermeasures. Creating lines of communication and standardizing procedures for exchanging information can greatly improve the group's capacity to counter threats.

Through these initiatives, the space sector can build a robust network of collaboration, driving forward innovation and ensuring a secure and sustainable future in space exploration and utilization. By implementing these solution guidelines, the space sector can address the current challenges in CIP, enhancing the resilience and security of these critical infrastructures. These measures not only mitigate risks but also support the sustainable growth and development of space activities.

4. EU-CIP Recommendations for R&I Activities and Roadmaps

Clear actions in line with the aforementioned guidelines and able to face the current and complex challenges are essential to strengthening space infrastructure and successfully addressing changing issues. In order to create, implement, and validate the effectiveness of relevant solutions, research and innovation (R&I) activities are essential. EU-CIP supports certain measures that can facilitate the implementation of the stated guidelines.

- **Recommendation 1 – evaluation of CIP/CIR actions in the space sector**

Space sector organizations should assess the degree of automation, sophistication, and comprehensiveness of their technology solutions and related CIP policies when determining their CIP/CIR measures. It is possible to use a five-level classification: "Excellent," "Very Good," "Good," "Fair," and "Poor." A high level of preparation in addressing the difficulties (C1-C7) and putting the solution recommendations (G1-G28) into practice is indicated by an "Excellent" maturity level. On the other hand, a "Poor" maturity level indicates that the majority of the issues and rules have not yet been resolved. An organization's level will have a direct impact on the strategic emphasis it places on R&I initiatives.

- **Recommendation 2 – Enhanced Regulatory Agility and International Policy Harmonization:**

Establish a flexible regulatory structure that can quickly adjust to the space industry's ever-changing danger scenario and technology environment. The goal of this framework should be to harmonize worldwide policy while tackling the issue of diverse regulatory environments in various jurisdictions (C1). A coalition of space-faring countries and industry players should be involved in order to

guarantee that the regulation modifications are thorough, progressive, and innovative while upholding strict security requirements. In addition, the framework must expedite the licensing procedure for ground stations, encourage international security protocol standardization, and enable the quick installation of robust space infrastructure (G8-G10, G12). This suggestion seeks to lower administrative barriers and establish a unified, safe, and effective operating environment for the international space community by promoting regulatory flexibility and cross-border collaboration.

- **Recommendation 3 – Integration of Activities and Implementation Guidelines in R&I Roadmaps:**

Research, technology development, regulatory auditing and validation, as well as training and reskilling programs, should all be included in space industry R&I roadmaps. Innovative space traffic management systems, strong satellite shielding, and improved satellite communication security are a few examples of technological recommendations. Activities targeted at promoting standardization and harmonizing international rules may fall under the category of regulatory support. Employee upskilling and training should concentrate on the unique requirements of the space industry, guaranteeing that staff members are prepared to efficiently administer and safeguard space infrastructure.

- **Recommendation 4 – Enhancing Collaborative Activities at the National and International Levels:**

According to guideline G22, R&I roadmaps ought to encourage national and international cooperation, which is essential for reducing fragmentation and boosting group capacity in the space industry. The goals of collaborative efforts should be to simplify processes, cut expenses by pooling resources, compile best practices, and make it easier to communicate important data. Such cooperation is necessary to promote innovation and provide a cohesive response to the intricate problems the space sector faces.

- **Recommendation 5 – Establishing a Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework:**

Space organizations and regulatory bodies have to set up systems for the ongoing assessment and observation of the R&I plan's implementation. This strategy may contain metrics to assess improvements in threat preparedness, response, risk mitigation effectiveness, operational continuity, regulatory compliance, and customer trust. The impact of research and innovation (R&I) initiatives on the industry's overall security posture and resilience, as well as how quickly it has adapted to the shifting regulatory environment and threat landscape, should also be quantified.

By implementing these suggestions, the space industry can promote a proactive, organized, and cooperative strategy for enhancing the security and resilience of space infrastructures, making sure they are prepared to handle the ever-complex regulatory, geopolitical, and technological environment.

5. The role of the EU-CIP project

EU-CIP plays a central role in promoting the security, resilience, and innovation of critical infrastructures. The mission of EU-CIP includes strengthening Europe's analytical capacities, amplifying the effects of research and innovation (R&I) endeavors, and building a strong ecosystem that links and facilitates stakeholders throughout the EU. In order to facilitate the implementation of

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guidelines and recommendations outlined above, the EU-CIP's coordination and support activities can support us.

1. Enhancing Europe's Analytical Capabilities (EU-CIP-ANALYSIS)

- **Addressing New Threats and Market Dynamics:** The space sector whitepaper emphasizes the emergence of new threats, particularly cyber-physical threats, and the rapid market dynamics, such as the increasing demand for high-speed internet in remote areas and the deployment of small satellites. EU-CIP's structured approach to collecting and analysing information about resilient infrastructures can provide crucial insights and foresight into these evolving threats and market needs, enabling the space sector to anticipate and prepare for future challenges more effectively.
- **Supporting Ground Segment Protection:** The whitepaper highlights the vulnerabilities of space ground segments to physical and cyber-attacks, stressing the need for a holistic framework for protection. EU-CIP's analytical capabilities, including its observatory of CIP/CIR research outcomes, technologies, policies, and standards, can provide valuable intelligence and best practices to enhance the protection of these critical space infrastructures.

2. Amplifying the Impact of R&I CIP/CIR Activities (EU-CIP-AMPLIFY)

- **Innovation in Ground Station Technology:** As the whitepaper notes the growth in satellite communication services and the need for robust ground station infrastructure, EU-CIP's innovation support services can play a crucial role. By identifying gaps in existing solutions and areas with significant innovation potential, EU-CIP can help drive the development and commercialization of advanced ground station technologies and resilient communication solutions.
- **Validating and Commercializing Space Innovations:** EU-CIP provides a virtualized testbed for experimenting with standards-based CIP/CIR solutions and certification schemes, which is particularly relevant for the space sector, known for its high R&D costs and the critical need for reliable and validated technologies.

3. Establishing a Vibrant Ecosystem (EU-CIP-ECOSYSTEM)

- **Promoting Cooperation in the Space Sector:** The space sector has a variety of issues, and the whitepaper emphasizes how stakeholders must work together to overcome them. This requirement is met by EU-CIP's goal of creating a Knowledge-Hub and creating a community around its analytical services and innovation support services. This initiative fosters knowledge exchange, teamwork, and a cohesive strategy for addressing the issues facing the space industry.
- **Participation in Standard and Policy Development:** The whitepaper emphasizes the value of regulatory backing and the unification of international space practices and technology. By fostering the participation of pertinent parties in policy formation and standardization initiatives, EU-CIP's ecosystem approach and active dissemination and communication strategy can guarantee that the demands and difficulties of the space industry are suitably addressed and supported at the policy level.

The EU-CIP's coordination and support initiatives are aligned with the space sector's unique requirements and policies, as delineated in the whitepaper. Through strengthening Europe's analytical capacities, increasing the influence of research and innovation endeavors, and creating a dynamic environment, EU-CIP not only facilitates but also drives the space industry toward more creativity, adaptability, and readiness to confront its distinct obstacles.

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Through the integration of its coordination and support functions, EU-CIP makes a substantial contribution to the space industry by strengthening its analytical capacities, increasing the effect of research and development endeavors, and creating a robust and interdependent ecosystem. This all-encompassing strategy is essential for encouraging innovation, guaranteeing the safety and robustness of space infrastructures, and assisting with the application of the policies and suggestions delineated in the space industry whitepaper [24].

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